

Determinants of Imports Demand in Sierra Leone; Application of Error Correction Model (1992 – 2022)

Alpha Kanu

Institute of Public Administration and Management, University of Sierra Leone

Email: alsteve88@gmail.com

Dr James L.S. Kollie

Institute of Public Administration and Management, University of Sierra Leone

Email: jkaylsu@yahoo.com

Emmanuel Jam Kamara

Institute of Public Administration and Management, University of Sierra Leone

Email: emmanuelkamarajam@gmail.com

Abstract:

This research utilizes an error correction model to investigate the behaviour of the determinants of imports demands in Sierra Leone using time series data for the period 1992 to 2022. ARDL modelling process was employed to capture the effect of real gross domestic product, real exchange rate, real interest rate and real export on imports demand. The results suggest that there exists a cointegrating relationship between import demand and its determinant. Results of the stationarity tests showed that the variables comprised of mixed series. Co-integration results also showed the existence of a unique long-run equilibrium. The long-run results showed that real GDP has a positive relationship with imports, and it is significant at the conventional level. A negative relationship was also found to exist between the exchange rate and imports and it was also significant. The short-run suggests that real export has the most influence on aggregate import demand in Sierra Leone. The real interest rate is however insignificant in both the long and short runs. These results imply that expenditure-reducing policies are more effective than exchange rate policies in correcting Sierra Leone's trade deficits.

Keywords:

Import Demand, Error Correction Model, Exchange rate, imperfect substitute model, Sierra Leone.

1.0 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

The determinants of imports have been the subject matter of many empirical studies in Sierra Leone. The offering of trade between nations to the extension process of economies has been of curiosity to many policymakers. Imports are central to trade between nations and the import of capital goods, in particular, is important to restoring economic growth, especially in countries with obstructed productivity. According to Tang (2003), the study of the import demand function has a relevant hidden meaning for macroeconomic policy issues. Most of which has been influenced by expenditure shifting over the exchange rate administration and commercial policy on a trade balance, and the level to which the exterior balance restrain affects a country's growth. Following Dutta and Ahmed (1991, 2001) there will be a need for testing the hypothesis of the existence of its major determinant using the counteraction technique developed by Johansen (1988, 1991) and Juselius (1990, 1994). With the application of the error-correction model (ECM) the study will estimate and integrate the motion of the short-run (changes) with the long run.

In terms of Sierra Leone, in general, is not distinct; the economy has observed a long era of an unfavourable trade balance. The exterior sector has been specified by structural trade deficits since the 1960s. By apprehending this unfavourable situation, the government undertake an import substitution (ISI) in the dead 60s as a quick means to arrive at economic development. The early years of the ISI development plan were somehow prosperous as the economy raised at a yearly average growth rate of almost 4 per cent merge with low inflation and sound foreign reserves. Apart from the formation of wean industries that never grew up, the ISI plan failed due to the fact that the wean industries created were mostly inefficient as they were not prone to international competition, followed by the low political will by the government officials to support the strategy. Irrationally, to finance such projects, the exports of cash crops and diamonds had to be intensified. The fall in the world prices of cash crops and the increase in smuggling activities of diamonds led to the eventual reduction in export revenues that no longer meet the growing import requirements. Hence, the terms of trade deteriorated and the economic growth in Sierra Leone also remained subdued slightly below the global economic growth of 3.6 per cent but higher than the Sub-Sahara average of 3.0 per cent in 2018.

Recently, economic expansion has been induced by mining especially iron ore. The economy is exposed to fluctuation in internal prices, the country main export by them are as follow; iron ore, diamond and rutile. Before 2014, as a way of supporting the government budget, the government had to rely on external help, but it was slowly becoming more independent. The Ebola outbreak in 2014 and 2015, joined with falling global commodities prices, caused a serious contraction of economic activities in all areas. The declaration of the end of the Ebola outbreak in Sierra Leone by W.H.O in November 2015, low commodity prices in 2015-2016 come up with the country's biggest fiscal shortfall since 2001. The increase in iron ore exports, coupled with the end of the Ebola epidemic, supported a resumption of economic growth in 2007. Investments and exports opportunities in the country were the main objectives of the formation of these institutions and also to assist and inform investors and exporters in the country. Despite the measures taken to bring about earthy changes in the trade balance, the falling trend could not be reversed. Rather the trade balance as a per cent of GDP deteriorated from an average of -2.24% from 1986 to 1990 to -3.72% from 1991 to 1995. This continued to worsen to -14.33% from 1996 to 2000 and then further deteriorated to -18.69% from 2001 to 2005. The ratio averaged -11.83% from 2006 to 2008. The real GDP growth continued to be weak in 2018 at 3.5% but improved slightly to an estimated 5.0% in 2019, driven by agriculture and service, and in the first half of 2019 by extractive, soured from the economic bulletin of Sierra Leone 2018. The economy of Sierra Leone has been affected by series of external factors that has leads to shortfall of trade balance, the occurrence of the COVID-19 outbreak seriously affect the foreign economy and the domestic economy which has resulted to a negative trade balance. The economy of Sierra Leone depends on the import sector, since the economy is not significantly strong in the production economy; hence there is a negative trade balance due to the economic shuck. The real GDP growth declined to 2.8% in 2022 from 4.1% in 2021 due to the impact of Russian's invasion of Ukraine. Growth was driven by mining exports (iron ore) on the demand side and by the recovery in key sectors on the supply side. Inflation rose to 26.1% in 2022 from 11.9% in 2021, driven by food and fuel inflation and depreciation of the leone. The fiscal deficit declined to an estimated 4.8% of GDP from 7.3% in 2021 due to higher grants. Public debt increased to an estimated 92.9% of GDP from 79.8% in 2021. The country remains at high risk of debt distress. The current account deficit narrowed to an estimated to 10.3%

Received: 22 November 2023

Revised: 1 December 2023

Final Accepted 7 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10284236>

of GDP from 15.0% in 2021, attributable to an improved trade balance and higher net transfers. The current account deficit is financed by the financial account. Gross foreign reserves fell to \$599.5 million (3.3 months of import cover) in September 2022 from \$932 million in December 2021 following measures to increase food and fuel supplies in local markets. The exchange rate depreciated sharply after mid-2021 due mainly to the widening trade deficit. The financial sector is underdeveloped but generally sound, with most indicators above the recommended minimum, except the nonperforming loans ratio (at 14.8% in 2021 against a regulatory target of 10%). Sierra Leone is characterized by high poverty (59.2% in 2020), income inequality (Gini coefficient of 0.357 in 2018), and high youth unemployment (70%), compounded by skills mismatch (African Development Bank, 2022).

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Sierra Leone external sector performance during the year (2018 to 2020) was driven largely by the worldwide economic crisis which continued in unabated declining per capita income, rapid inflation and a severe external payments problem has a straightforward explanation. This poor economic performance could be attributed mainly to the failing world demand and export prices, to local currency against major international currencies and declining foreign inflow and export volumes. Since independence, the economy's prosperity was based on the boost in the export sector powered by the mining sector. While these exports grew, the economy prospered, when they began an irreversible decline, prosperity changed to stagnation and then decline. Given Sierra Leone's dependency on international trade, the need for the reversal of the import and export trends cannot be overemphasized. The trade deficit widened slightly to US\$ 643.7 million in 2020 from US\$ 623.2 million in 2018. This was mainly due to the 2.3 per cent drop in exports earnings in 2020, from US\$ 567 million in 2018 to US\$ 554 million in 2019, combined with the marginal increase (0.6 per cent) in merchandise imports to US\$ 1197.7 million from US\$ 1190.2 million in 2018. Attaining this requires a clearer understanding of the merchandise import and export flows in Sierra Leone. This may help immensely in the prescription and implementation of policies geared towards import contraction, export expansion or a combination of both.

This study will generally analyse the structure and model that determine the demand for import of goods and services and their various determinants in Sierra Leone. It will also verify an assessment of the elasticity of import demand to the various determinants of aggregate import and their components, and determines whether import demand functions had shifted during the period under consideration. To achieve the general objective, the following specific objectives must be pursued:

- To validate the view that foreign exchange constraints significantly influence import demand in Sierra Leone.
- To determine whether the variables that mostly explains the variation of import demand in Sierra Leone are co-integrated with each other with the application of the error correction model.
- To bring in policy conclusions for imports from the experimental results.

This study will make a diverse contribution to the existing literature. First, this will help to estimate these duplex questions of economic growth; it impacts on effects of imports with the latest time-series data on Sierra Leone. Second and maybe more importantly, in most developing countries, the idea of imports has different perspectives. An increase in imports only results in a negative trade, looking at the trade balance. Contrary, a fall in tariff revenue as well as make worse the inflationary tendencies of the domestic country may result from a reduction or a restriction in a county import level. To deal with these difficulties, if the study can estimate what determines the demand of Sierra Leone's imports and examine the relationship between import demand and its determinants the research may be of much help. Also, it will provide policymakers with experimental evidence on the major determinants of Sierra Leone's imports which will help them draw up better strategies to improve the balance of trade problems in the economy. This research paper is being organized into five different sections and is organized as follows: Section 1 provides the introduction and gives a detail of the current economic situation. Section 2 deals with the literature review. The methodology is laid out in section 3, whereas section 4 contain the empirical analysis with the summary and conclusion being the last section.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Received: 22 November 2023

Revised: 1 December 2023

Final Accepted 7 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10284236>

2.1 THEORETICAL REVIEW

As it is shown in the introductory aspect of our discussion, Sierra Leone's economy is highly dependent on imports for both consumption and production. Virtually all the major industrial raw materials are sourced from abroad while the country depends wholly on foreign supply for intermediate and capital goods. Production for exports is highly elastic because the major export products are primary producers whose prices have been on the downward trend and exogenously determined. Besides, these exports are slow in responding to exchange rate adjustment. The theoretical framework for the determination of trade volumes and price is a similar one since it stems from the general demand and production theory. In import determinants, two major models of trade have dominated the literature- the perfect and imperfect substitute models.

2.1.1 PERFECT SUBSTITUTE MODEL

This model assumes perfect substitutability between domestic and expatriate goods. The main idea of this model is that each country can be an exporter or an importer of goods, but not coupled at the same time. The perfect substitute model doesn't have a separate import demand function; instead, the demand for imports is represented by the excess demand for local goods. This implies that evaluating or forecasting import demand for a perfectly substitutable good is a matter of forecasting local demand with imports appearing as the remains. Also, there is only one price in the perfect substitute model. The rationale is once we abstract from transportation costs and other trade barriers and express all prices in a common currency, and then there is only one-traded goods price. This world price is determined by the interaction of world supply and demand for the traded good. In other words, a nation may only affect the price of traded goods to an extent that it can affect world supply or demand.

According to Goldstein and Kan 1985, in as much as this model has not been observed in the real world situation, this model has drawn much less attention in the experimental studies than the imperfect substitute model.

2.1.2 IMPERFECT SUBSTITUTE MODEL

The model states that neither imports nor exports are the perfect substitute for locally made goods to the representative nation. Imperfect substitute models also assume that prices move to equate demand and supply in each period. However, economies theory [for example Hay (1950)] argues that firms will attempt to balance the cost of changing prices to the cost of other adjustment measures such as changing inventories. Therefore if the market clearing property of the imperfect substitute model is to be retained, then non-price rationing variables should be included in both the import and export equation so that price changes alone are not presented as the sole catalyst for market clearing conditions. Alternatively, observed trade quantities and prices have been postulated to reflect markets in disequilibrium with partial adjustment mechanisms being specified accordingly.

The partial adjustment mechanism is very popular with researchers because the results obtained have been generally satisfactory and easily interpreted. Despite its popularity, this mechanism imposes a restrictive dynamic structure in the data, which will be more desirable to test rather than impose a priori. The realization that variables such as real income and imports can be decomposed into a stationary and a non-stationary component has called for the adoption of a more flexible dynamic specification of trade data. Consequently, the co-integration technique has been used to address the inherent specification problem in the partial adjustment mechanism.

2.2 EMPIRICAL LITERATURE

According to Abrishami and Mehrara for Iran investigate the determinants of import demand for consumer, intermediate and capital goods over the period from 1971 to 1999. In their empirical estimation, they incorporate the bound test and their findings reveal that the lateral market exchange rate is the key determinant of import demand. Dutta and Ahmed (2004) did a similar study for India using Johannsen's co-integration model on time series data from 1971 to 1995. From their estimation, they stated that import demand is a function of relative import price, import liberalisation and gross domestic product. Their findings show that the income variable is the most important determinant of India's import. Also, it showed that import demand is less prone to change in price, which reflects on the non-competitive nature of Indians import demand.

Received: 22 November 2023

Revised: 1 December 2023

Final Accepted 7 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10284236>

Using the ARDL approach of cointegration, Hye and Mashkooor estimated for Bangladesh aggregate import demand function, using data from 1980 to 2018. From their empirical findings the relationship between imports, national income and relative prices is been confirm by the long run estimation. GDP is favourable and to a certain extend inelastic while relative price elasticity is unfavourable in the long run. The estimation is done by Chang, Ho and Heng (2005) for South Korea on the aggregate import demand function from 1980 to 2000. Findings show that the volume of imports, income and relative prices are all cointegrated. The estimated long-run (short-run) elasticities of imports demand for income and relative price are 1.86 (0.86) and -0.2 (-0.05), respectively. The empirical analysis on South Africa's aggregate import demand function was done by Thaver and Ekanayeke (2010) from 1950 to 2008. Their finding includes external reserves as an unconventional variable in their model, unlike other studies, because they attest that external reserves favourable influence import demand. A long-run relationship exists between imports and their determinants were suggested in their findings. However, their study reveals that discrimination has had a positive short-run negative impact on import demand, but is negative in the long run. Furthermore, international sanctions affected import demand positively in the short-run, but negatively in the long run. Import demand function was determined for Madagascar and Mauritius by two researchers Razafimahefa and Hamori in 2005 for these two economies by using the bond test method implemented by Pesaran in 2001. Their research shows the existence of a cointegration relationship and shows that the long-run income and price elasticities are as follows 0.855 and 20.487 for Madagascar and 0.671 and 20.644 for Mauritius. These two economies import demand respond to similar relative prices.

A method of cointegration was used by Tang (2003) to estimate china's aggregate import demand function from 1970 to 1999. In addition to the conventional setting for the above-mentioned topic, the author abducted another factor believed to have affected domestic activity. These may include national cash flow and final expenditure components. The statistical results suggested that a long-run equilibrium relationship between these measures of internal activity and China's import demand. In general, domestic activity and relative prices are inelastic in the long run.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Model Specification

3.1.1 The Imperfect Substitute Model

This model assumes that either imports or exports are perfect substitutes for the domestic goods of the country under consideration (Yue, 2010). Looking at the literature, it might be seen that quite a several approaches were used in estimating import demand. However, this study follows the imperfect substitute model by Yue, 2010.

To accomplish this research effectively, there is a need to represent the study in a functional form which is thus specified:

$$M_t = f(RGDP_t, RER_t, MS_t, X_t, D_t) \text{ ----- (1)}$$

Where

RGDP_t = Real GDP

RER_t = Real Exchange Rate

MS_t = Money Supply

X_t = Export

D_t = Dummy Variable

Representing the above in log-linear econometric form:

$$\ln M_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln RGDP_t + \beta_2 \ln REER_t + \beta_3 \ln RIR_t + \beta_4 \ln X_t + \beta_6 D_t + \varepsilon_t \text{ -----(2)}$$

From equation (2) in time t, the vulnerable variable is the import volume which is represented by M, and the independent variable used to predict include real gross domestic product represented by RGDP_t, real effective exchange rate which is REER_t; is the real interest rate represented by RIR_t and X_t represent exchange rate; D_t and ε_t represent the dummy variable and the error term respectively.

Received: 22 November 2023

Revised: 1 December 2023

Final Accepted 7 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10284236>

Where, $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6$ are the respective parameter.

Following Pesaran, et al (2010) in distinguishing the short run from the long-run drift, the above equation (2) must be determined in an error correctional model (ECM) format, which has been used in many concluded recent studies, including Thaver and Ekanayeke (2010), Chang, Ho and Huang (2005), and Tang (2002). The long-run equilibrium state of import demand has been specified in the above equation. However, for policy reasons, the short-run adjustment of imports to changes in its determinants is necessary. To capture the speed adjustment we estimate the following dynamic error correction model:

$$\Delta \ln M_t = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_1 \Delta \ln M_{t-i} + \sum \gamma_i \Delta \ln \text{RGDP}_{t-i} + \sum \eta_i \Delta \ln \text{REER}_{t-i} + \sum \theta_i \Delta \ln \text{RIR}_{t-i} + \sum \sigma_i \Delta \ln X_{t-i} + \beta_1 D_{1t} + \lambda_1 \ln M_{t-1} + \lambda_2 \ln \text{RGP}_{t-1} + \lambda_3 \ln \text{RFR}_{t-1} + \lambda_4 \text{RIR}_{t-1} + \lambda_5 \ln X_{t-1} + \omega_t \text{-----} \quad (3)$$

Where Δ represents the first difference operator.

3.4 Estimation Techniques

In examining the cointegration relationship between imports and its determinants, the study used the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bound sampling process developed by Pesaran, et al (2001). In terms of advantages, the ARDL has several advantages over other cointegration techniques. One of the main advantages of this approach lies in the fact that it can be applied irrespective of whether the variables are $I(0)$ or $I(1)$ (Pesaran and Pesaran 1997). This model takes sufficient lags to trap generating process in a specific modelling framework, looking at the other advantage. Moreover, according to Pesaran and Shin, 1999 this model is known to have small exceptional sample property than that of Johansen cointegration techniques. The ARDL bounds test approach developed by Pesaran et al. (2001) is grounded on two distinctive ordinary steps. The first step includes using an F-test or Wald test to test for a mutual significance of no cointegration. This test is done using Equation (2). Two critical values for a given significant level with and without a time factor by Pesaran et al 2001. It is assumed that variables are integrated in order zero $I(0)$ and order one $I(1)$. If the F-value estimated surpasses the upper critical value, we reject H_0 indicating cointegration between the dependent variables, if the F-value fall below the critical bound values, H_0 will be rejected immediately and finally, if the F-value fall within the

bounds, the result will be inconclusive. From the evidence of cointegration, the next logical step involves estimating the short-run and long-run coefficients of the cointegrated model (Pesarin et. al., 2001).

Also, to estimate if a long-run relationship exists among the variables, this study uses the Autoregressive Distributive Lags (ARDL) Bounds testing approach developed by Pesaran and Shin (1998) and later expanded by Pesaran et al. (2001). Also, with the help of using this approach, one is allowed to estimate short-run, long-run effects simultaneously by forming an Error Correction Model (ECM) derived from the ARDL model without loss of long-term information. In order to avoid this, there was a need to use the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test to find out there is a unit root in each series. The findings reflect the unit root hypothesis of the estimated DF statistic is less than the tabulated critical value for the five per cent significance level. Finally, by using CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests, this paper will also be able to check the stability of the parameters of the model.

3.4 Source of Data

To allow for a wide range of stability tests, this study suggests yearly data for 1980 to 2018. Efforts are made to provide a well comprehensive data using mostly secondary data gathered from the Bank of Sierra Leone (BSL) annual reports and all the variables were sourced from the World Development Indicators (WDI). THE dependent import variable was transformed into a natural logarithm; the remaining variables that would be used are real GDP, real interest rate, real effective exchange rate, and Export.

The sample for the current study is a compromise of time-series considering the period of 1992-2022. Regression analysis is conducted to ascertain the determinants of import demand and their impact on economic growth. The data used in this study will be tested for stationarity using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) modelling process. The test is essential so that the correct transformations can be made to ensure we obtain the stationarity process. The hypothesis will be tested using the ordinary least square (OLS) regression method on various equations to obtain their estimate. The estimation of an Error Correction Model (ERM) follows the observation that there is cointegration.

4. EMPIRICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Received: 22 November 2023

Revised: 1 December 2023

Final Accepted 7 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10284236>

4.1 UNIT ROOT TEST

The bound test ARDL model to cointegration theoretically does not crave foregoing testing of the time series for unit roots, but to establish the time-series properties of the relevant variables, there is a need to conduct a standard unit root test. However, following Jalil et al 2008, it is important to carry on this test to validate that the variables are not integrated of order than one, and also the testing of unit root is necessary to avoid the problem of phoney results stated by some current empirical studies. Hence, to make sure that some variables are not integrated in greater order, there is a need to estimate the process with unit root tests. Because of this, before applying the (ARDL) approach to cointegration, unit root tests were conducted to investigate the stationarity properties of the data. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Philips Perron tests were used to all variables in level and also the first difference were to determine their ordering of integration and confirm stationarity. The results of the unit root tests of both Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Philips Perron with intercepts only in the model for all variables are shown below.

Table 1: RESULTS OF UNIT ROOT FOR STATIONARITY

Variables	Augmented Dickey-Fuller		Philips Perron		Order of integration
	Level	1 st difference	Level	1 st difference	
LNM	-0.502809	-6.081219	-0.639697	-6.109500	I(1)
RGDP	0.230978	-5.345601	0.325241	-10.79462	I(1)
RIR	-1.512060	-6.577302	-3.780034	-6.326127	I(0)
REER	-1.389133	-3.7202795	-1.715808	-3.481483	I(1)
X	-2.883052	-7.939471	-2.890732	-7.939471	I(0)

Source: authors' computation (Eviews)

Critical Value at 5% = 2.8830

Looking at the unit root test results shown in table 1 above, the results show that the lagged of import, real GDP, and real exchange rate turn out to be stationary at first difference. However, the real interest rate and export are stationary at a level. The decision rules state that we accept the null hypothesis if the absolute critical value at 5% level significance is greater than the absolute t-statistic value. From table 2 above, it is clear that the corresponding critical values at a level for each of I (0) variables is greater than the t-statistics values, hence we accept the null hypothesis at the level and conclude that the variables are non-stationary. But at the first difference, the corresponding critical value at 5% is less than the t-statistic for the variable, and we, therefore, reject the null hypothesis and accept and accept the alternative hypothesis.

The results in table 2 show that LNM, RGDP, and REER are stationary at the first difference, but real interest rate RIR and export X are stationary at level. The result thus reinforces the use of the bond test to determine the cointegration relationship among the series.

4.2 BOUND TEST FOR COINTEGRATION

Cointegration is a test to check the existence of a long-run relationship among the variables. Initially, Engle and Granger 1987 introduced the concept of cointegration. Later on, following the extension of the following researchers Stock and Watson 1988, Johansen 1988, 1991, 1992, 1995, Johansen and Juselius 1990, Pesaran and Shin 1999 and Pesaran et al. 2001. Johansen and Juselius 1990 approach and Pesaran et al. 2001 approaches are extensively used approaches to cointegration. This study uses abound testing approach to cointegration, within an Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) framework, to determine the determinants of import demand in Sierra Leone, developed by Pesaran and Shin 1999 and Pesaran et al. 2001.

In order to test the existence of the long-run relationship among the selected variables irrespective of whether they are integrated of order zero I(0) order one I(1) or mixed, unlike other available approaches to cointegration. This approach is based on the estimates of an Unrestricted Error Correction Model (ECM) and is likely to have better statistical properties since it does not restrict the short-run dynamics and long-run equilibrium to the residual term.

In estimating the bounds testing approach, the model makes use of estimated equation (2) in the previous chapter using the ARDL approach to cointegration. The assumption of the ARDL approach, the calculated F-statistics is compared against the critical values. The decision rules state that the null hypothesis, of no-integration, must be accepted if the F-statistic is less than the lower bound. However, if the f-statistic is less than the lower bound, the test fails to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that the long-run relationship does not exist. Thus, the results of the bound test are computed below in table 2.

Table 2: ARDL BOUND TEST FOR COINTEGRATION RESULT

Test Statistics	Value	Significance		I(0)	I(1)
			Asymptotic N = 1000		
F-statistic	6.012711	10%		2.26	3.35
K	5	5%		2.62	3.79
		2.5%		2.96	4.18
		1%		3.41	4.68

Source: authors' computation (Eviews)

The results of the trace test are reported in the table above. It is observed that the calculated F-statistic 6.012711 is the highest than the calculated upper bounds critical value of 4.68 at the 5% significant level. This simply shows that the null hypothesis of no cointegration is rejected at the 5% level of significance and is a cointegration relationship among imports and its major determinants. This is used in confirming the existence of an underlying steady state long-run relationship among variables, i.e. the dependent and explanatory variables in log form. This suggests that the dependent variable drift together with the independent variables for a long time frame. The long-run results are reported in table 3.

4.3 ARDL LONG-RUN RELATIONSHIP

Received: 22 November 2023

Revised: 1 December 2023

Final Accepted 7 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10284236>

Having established that import demands are cointegrated with its determinants, it is now necessary to estimate the long-run elasticity using the appropriate lag length. The estimated model presented here is based on Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). The results of the long-run elasticity are reported in table 3 below.

Table 3: ARDL Long Run Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic	Probability
REER	-0.006867	0.002677	-2.564962	0.0164
RGDP	4.40E-13	8.24E-14	5.337635	0.0000
RIR	-0.022965	0.014930	-1.538231	0.1361
X	-0.022959	0.020450	-1.122699	0.2718
DUMMY	0.018439	0.358610	0.051418	0.9594

Source: authors' computation (Eviews)

The long-run results indicate that export is statistically insignificant. This means that an increase in imports may not affect the demand for imports in Sierra Leone, since the major import in Sierra Leone is petroleum products, machinery and capital goods that are essential for continuing economic activities in Sierra Leone.

The results also reveal that the estimated real GDP is positive and statically significant at the 1 per cent level. This is showing that in the long run, a 1 per cent increase in real GDP increases aggregates import demand to 4.4%. Although the long-run coefficient of the real exchange rate is negative but it is statically significant, which means that the devaluation may decrease the demand for real aggregate import because the increase in devaluation increase import bills. Long-run results also indicate that the real interest rate is negative and statistically insignificant. The present result suggests that a higher interest rate will lead to higher inflation.

The result from the long-run estimated in the table below shows that real export X, real interest rate RIR, and war dummy (DUM) are found insignificant in explaining the dependent variable at the normal level of 5 per cent.

4.4 SHORT-RUN DYNAMICS ARDL 1,2,0,0,1

Having established the long-run relationship, we now proceed to specify an error correction model as follows:

$$DLNM = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 D(RGDP_t) + \alpha_2 DREER_t + \alpha_3 DRIR_t + \alpha_4 DX_t + \alpha_5 DUM + \alpha_6 DLM_{t-1} + \alpha_7 ECT_{t-1} \quad (4)$$

Equation (3) is the error correction model (ECM) for the demand for imports in Sierra Leone. ECT is the lag of the residuals of equation (2) and is also known as the error correction term. D signifies the second difference and all other terms are defined as above in equation (2). To establish the short-run relationship we estimated the error correction model. The coefficient of the lagged residuals should be statistically significant and negative to confirm our earlier findings of cointegration. The results of the estimation of the error correction term also known as the differential equation are represented in table 4 below.

From the results shown in table 4 below, one may see the coefficient of the lagged residual is negative and significant at the 1% level. This supports our earlier findings of a cointegrating relationship between the variables. The coefficient of -0.41 implies that 41% of the short-run distortions adjust in the long run. In the case of Sierra Leone, we can see that the real export X is positive and statistically significant in explaining import demand in Sierra Leone in the short run; these findings imply that a 1 per cent increase in export will result in a 0.11 per cent increment in aggregate import demand. The findings further show that the real exchange rate has a negative coefficient and is statistically insignificant in the short run.

Ultimately, the coefficient of the dummy for war was found out to be statistically significant but with a negative sign. This implies that the impact of civil war is insignificant on import demand in the short run. This is a realistic situation as the short-run effects of the civil war are only felt in the remote areas of the country where import goods demand are very low.

Table 4: Short Run Results (1, 2, 0, 0, 1)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic	Probability
C	7.829742	1.505458	5.200903	0.0000
D(REER)	-0.000272	0.000888	-0.306692	0.7615
D(REER(-1))	0.002453	0.001004	2.442320	0.0217
D(X)	0.011427	0.006426	1.778144	0.0871
D(DUMMY)	-0.302736	0.168442	-1.797276	0.0839
ECT(-1)	-0.411551	0.079437	-5.180863	0.0000
R-squared	0.593950	Mean dependent var		0.034750
Adjusted R-squared	0.528458	S. D dependent var		0.328017
S.E of regression	0.225246	Akaike info criterion		0.004146
Sum squared resid	1.572808	Schwarz criterion		0.265376
Log likelihood	5.923301	Hannan-Quin criter.		0.096242
F-statistic	9.069039	Durbin-Watson stat		2.183561
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000022			

Source: authors' computation (Eviews)

4.5 STABILITY TEST

Stability analysis of parameters has become a very important task in the most modern empirical analysis. Such analysis helps the researcher to identify the presence of any structural breaks in the data generating process. Unexpected shifts in time series data can lead to major forecasting errors. Hence these shifts need to be recognized and fixed. The CUSUM and CUSUMQ are used to investigate this problem in our underlying generating series, which may influence the stability of the parameters.

Received: 22 November 2023

Revised: 1 December 2023

Final Accepted 7 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10284236>

FIGURE 1: RESULT OF CUSUM TEST FOR STABILITY

FIGURE 2: RESULT OF CUSUM OF SQUARE TEST FOR STABILITY

SUMMARY CONCLUDING REMARKS AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The main purpose of this research is to understand the determinants of import demand in Sierra Leone by assessing a dynamic import demand function by adopting an error correction model (ECM). To achieve this goal, a brief literature review on the theoretical and empirical analysis of determinants of import demand was undertaken. As seen in the literature review chapter, there is a remarkable consensus in the profession on the empirical form of the demand for imports. Real effective exchange rate and real GDP are considered the most significant determinants, however, real interest rate and inflation and country-specific characteristics have been known to play significant roles in determining imports demand especially when dealing with developing countries.

For the achievement of the general objectives of this study, the study used time series data from World Development Indicators (WDI) for empirical analysis by estimating the specified import demand functions from 1992 to 2022 within the framework of the ARDL estimation technique. The results of these estimations show that the imports demand function conforms mostly to economic theory with statistically significant estimates. The econometric properties are also very satisfactory and the model can be used for policy analysis and forecasting purposes. Next, the study conducted a unit root test using the Augmented Dicky-fuller (ADF) and Philip-Peron to determine whether the variables specified in the imports demand equation are stationary. The result of these tests showed that while real interest rate and export were stationary at level, all other variables were stationary at first difference. That is, the study comprises both I (0) and I (1) variables.

The study employed the lag length criteria in selecting the optimal number of lags and each of the five (5) criteria selected an optimal lag length of two (2).

Then, the study conducted the ARDL bound test for co-integration to determine whether there exists long-run equilibrium. Having established bound test for co-integration, the conclusion was reached as a result of the f-statistics, which was greater than the I (0) and I (1) bounds at the

conventional level of significance, this study then proceeds to treat the data from the ills of spurious correlation by specifying an error correction model for the import demand equation of Sierra Leone. The long-run finding shows that the exchange rate and real GDP were the most significant variables on imports demand during the period of study. Both variables were significant at the conventional level. Even though other variables had a prior expected sign, they were found to be statistically insignificant at the 5% level of significance.

The short-run result shows that not all the variables were statistically significant at the 5% level, only real export and war dummy which had a negative impact on demand for imports in the short-run. The error correction term had the expected negative and significance at the 1% level in the short-run dynamic. The coefficient also reveals a slow adaption procedure to long-run disequilibrium. Thus, 41% of any previous disequilibrium in imports demand is corrected in the current year. The model is steady as showed by the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ, whilst the Jarque-Bera test disclosed that the residuals are conventionally distributed. There is no evidence of heteroscedasticity and serial correlation.

The findings of the current study lend support to studies done elsewhere on imports demand. For example, Moran (1989) finds that in twenty-one LDCs the policies traditionally considered (i.e., policies that exclusively affect income or relative prices) will have a limited impact on imports demand. Thus, broader policies, which focus on affecting the availability of foreign exchange, should be pursued, as they are likely to yield a larger impact on the volume of imports.

5.2 Policy Recommendations and Concluding Remarks

The regression results show that the most significant influence on import demand in Sierra Leone is the real effective exchange rate and real GDP in the long run, while in the short run is export. The government thus needs to take steps to bridge the gap between the exchange rate at the parallel market and the official exchange rate. The government can take the following steps to achieve this goal.

- Upon the close monitoring of activities of commercial banks and foreign exchange bureaus. It has been a common practice for these institutions not to sell foreign exchange at their

advertised prices. The claim is that the managers of these institutions sell hard currency in the parallel markets via hawkers known as "dollar boys." Huge penalties that may lead to a withdrawal of operational increases should be levied on banks and bureaus that refuse to desist from such practices. For policy recommendation, the findings of this research suggest that fiscal policies made to affect the pattern of expenditure on the final components, particularly private consumption and the government are essential to reduce the imports of goods and hence mitigate external imbalances.

- The relevant influence of external reserve availability as a refrainment factor in estimating imports demand suggests that an increase in external reserves will move readily influencing import behaviour. These policies would have to be accustomed toward export promotion. The suggestion of the foregoing in Sierra Leone are therefore that trade policy should move away from import substitution towards export promotion to help support economic expansion over imports while curtailing the deleterious effects on the balance of payment.
- The ineffectiveness of exchange rate policy in influencing imports demand reveals the large influence of demand components on import demand also. The implication is that in correcting Sierra Leone's trade deficits expenditure reducing policies are more effective than exchange rate policies. To mitigate such it will be better for the government to create the possible environment to boost local (domestic) production capacity to reduce imports, especially on consumers goods like rice which can be produced locally. Moreover, the removal of government subsidies on consumable goods and hence reduce the imports bills. Finally, with an increment of domestic capacity, the export base will be broadened, which is likely to boost export receipts and hence reduce the trade deficits.
- A similar scheme should be established for small-scale farmers that farm cash crops. These farmers should be encouraged to do group exporting and through Sierra Leone Export Development and investment corporation (SLEDIC) all necessary arrangements for the exports of their products can be facilitated and processed. To prevent the situation where all of the generated foreign exchange is spent on importing essentials, the manufacturing sector should be promoted especially agro-based and import-substituting industries. Attracting foreign investment to this sector should be a goal for the government.

- Finally, it is suggested that the government should embark on an export promotion strategy. Such a policy can be achieved through price incentives to exporters, and also through the promotion of non-traditional exports. Also, export diversification and the provision of basic infrastructure in the rural areas, as well as the supply of inputs at affordable prices, may provide an additional boost to export performance. The government should also pursue an outward-oriented strategy.

The determinants of import demand have been thoroughly investigated over the years because the data is rich and the value of import extends over long periods. Traditional trade models posit imports as a positive function of domestic capacity and a negative function of relative prices. These models assume that the importing country is not constrained by foreign exchange availability. However, Hemphill and others have shown that the availability or non-availability of foreign currency needed to buy imported goods significantly influence import decisions in developing countries.

However, the success of the obvious looking policies that boost the accessibility of foreign exchange depends critically on the surplus to the external market and on the ability to expand capital inflows. In the absence of these essentials being met, foreign exchange availability would continue to be restrained. This implication by policymakers who buttress that who are willing to expand their import would not be able to impact the behaviour of imports suitably (Mwega1993).

Due to the lack of data in developing countries, most studies have dealt with aggregate import functions. It is important to note that the results of this study could have been improved if imports were disaggregated, the lack of available disaggregated information for Sierra Leone makes specifying disaggregated functions impossible. However, while disaggregation may be preferable in principle since it usually results in more information when the data is accurate and well-specified; there has been some controversy on its merits in practice. As noted by Grunfeld and Griliches (1960), Aigner and Goldfeld (1974), disaggregated data are generally subjected to larger measurement errors and are therefore likely to be misspecified than aggregated relationships. Based on these arguments and given the fact that there are various gaps and missing series in the disaggregated data for Sierra Leone, the study only estimated aggregate relationships.

Some studies dealing with import have considered import supply and specified a reduced form equation that depicts an equilibrium relationship between import demand and supply. The reduced form equations usually have the domestic capacity of the trading partners as an additional variable. Given Sierra Leone's economic size with its trading partners, domestic policies could not influence activities in the economy of its partners. Sierra Leone can only react to policies implemented by its trading partners; therefore there is no need to discuss the supply side of import in Sierra Leone. In the instance where trading partners' economies are comparable in size, and the two-way trade volume is significant, the inclusion of this variable might be relevant to policy analysts.

Acknowledgement

This study was financially supported by the Institute of Public Administration and Management (IPAM), Sierra Leone. The authors are grateful for their assistance.

References

- [1] Abbott, A. J. and Seddighi, H. R. (1996) 'Aggregate imports and expenditure components in the UK: an empirical analysis', *Applied Economics*, Vol. 28, pp. 1119-1125.
- [2] Abu Bakarr Trawalie (2003) "Real exchange rate and trade balance in Sierra Leone, pp 83-86.
- [3] Bahmani-Oskooee, M. and Niroomand, F. (1998) 'Long-run price elasticities and the Marshall-Lerner condition revisited', *Economics Letters*, Vol. 61, pp. 101-109.
- [4] Bank of Sierra Leone, *Bulletin* (2013), Various Issues.
- [5] Bathalomew, D. (2008) "An econometric estimation of the Aggregate Import Function for Sierra Leone," Department of Economics, *Journal of Monetary and Economic Integration* Vol. 10, No. 1, University of Sierra Leone.
- [6] Chang, T., Y. Ho, and Huang, C. (2005) 'A re-examination of South Korea's aggregate import demand function: a bounds test analysis', *Journal of Economic Development*, Vol. 30, pp. 119-128.

- [7] Dutta, D. and N. Ahmed (2001), "An Aggregate Import Demand Fund for India; A Cointegration Analysis" <http://eprints.anu.edu.au/archive/00001731/>.
- [8] Egwaikhide, F. E. (1999) 'Determinants of imports in Nigeria: a dynamic specification', AERC Research Paper, No. 91.
- [9] Frimpong, J. M. and Oteng-Abayie, E. F. (2006) 'Aggregate import demand and expenditure components in Ghana: an econometric analysis', MPRA Paper, No. 599.
- [10] Gafar, J. S. (1988) 'The determinants of import demand in Trinidad and Tobago: 1967-84', Applied Economics, Vol. 20, pp. 303-313.
- [11] Gumede, V. (2000) 'Import demand elasticities for South Africa: a cointegration analysis', Journal for Studies in Economics and Econometrics, Vol. 24, pp. 21-37.
- [12] Goldstein, M. and Khan, M. S. (1985) 'Income and price effects in foreign trade', in R.W. Jones and P.B. Kenen (eds.) Handbook of International Economics, Vol. II, New York: Elsevier Science Publications, pp. 1041-1105.
- [13] Hemphill, W. (1974) "The effect of Foreign Exchange Receipts on Imports of Less Developed Countries" IMF Staff Papers, Vol. XXI No.3, pp. 637-77.
- [14] Ho, W. S. (2004) 'Estimating Macao's import demand functions', Monetary Authority of Macao, 18.
- [15] Hong, P. (1999) 'Import elasticities revisited', Discussion Paper No. 10, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, United Nations.
- [16] Khan, M.S. (1974) "Import and export demand in developing Countries" IMF Staff Papers, Vol. XXI No.3, pp. 678-693.
- [17] Mohammed, H. A. and Tang, T.C. (2000) 'Aggregate imports and expenditure components in Malaysia: a cointegration and error correction analysis', ASEAN Economic Bulletin, Vol. 17, pp. 257-69.

- [18] Moran, C. (1989), "Imports under a Foreign Exchange Constraint" *The World Bank Economic Review*, Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 249-95.
- [19] Mweya, F. M. (1993) 'Import demand elasticities and stability during trade liberalization: a case study of Kenya', *Journal of African Economies*, Vol. 2, pp. 381-416.
- [20] Pesaran, M. H., and Pesaran, B. (1997) 'Working with Microfit 4.0: interactive econometric analyses', Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- [21] Pesaran, M. H. and Shin, Y. (1999) 'An autoregressive distributed lag modeling approach to cointegration analysis', in Strom, S. (Ed.): *Econometrics and Economic Theory in 20th Century: The Ragnar Frisch Centennial Symposium*, Chapter 11, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- [22] Sinha, D. (1997) 'Determinants of import demand in Thailand', *International Economic Journal*, Vol. 11, pp. 73-83.
- [23] Tang and Nair, M. (2002) "A cointegration analysis of Malaysian import demand function: reassessment from the bounds test", *Applied Economic Letters*, Vol. 9, No. 5, pp. 293-6.
- [24] Tang, T. C. (2003) 'An empirical analysis of China's aggregate import demand function', *China Economic Review*, Vol. 12, No. 2, pp. 142-63.
- [25] Xu, X. (2002) 'The dynamic-optimizing approach to import demand: a structural model', *Economics Letters*, Vol. 74, pp. 265–270.